

ISic1161

I.Sicily inscription 1161

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]Φολοινία[---]
2. [---]αίου(vac.undefin)κα[---]
3. [---]Φολοινί[---]
4. [---]ματήρ[---]

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492773

EDCS 39102317

PHI 140646

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0341 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Brugnone, A. 1974. Iscrizione greche del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos*. 20: 218-264. At 12

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 199 = 351

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